

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES REGARDING BIOMEDICAL WASTE MANAGEMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS AT DISTRICT HEADQUARTERS HOSPITAL, PARACHINAR, DISTRICT KURRAM

Bibi Fatima^{*1}, Ahmad Ullah², Yawar Abbas³, Andalib Hassan⁴, Muhammad Hassanain⁵,
Tasawar Hussain⁶, Haider Ali⁷, Haider Ali Shah⁸, Kashif Anar⁹

^{*1,2,3,4,5,6}Khyber Medical University, Institute of Health Sciences (IHS), Kurram, Pakistan

⁹Demonstrator, Khyber Medical University, Institute of Health Sciences (IHS), Kurram, Pakistan

¹bibifatimasherazi@gmail.com, ²hafizahmadkhan.9@gmail.com, ³yawarabbas935@gmail.com,
⁴hassanandalib9@gmail.com, ⁵muhammadhassanain77@gmail.com, ⁶tasawar56u@gmail.com
⁷asas1212.ha91@gmail.com, ⁸alihaiderrfakhri110@gmail.com
⁹kashif.ihskurram@kmu.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Bibi Fatima

Abstract

Background:

Biomedical waste (BMW) is generated during the diagnosis, treatment, or immunization of patients and includes infectious materials, sharps, and other hazardous substances. Improper biomedical waste management can lead to serious health risks for healthcare workers, patients, and the community, as well as environmental pollution.

Objective:

To assess the knowledge and practices regarding biomedical waste management among healthcare providers at District Headquarters (DHQ) Hospital, Parachinar, District Kurram.

Materials and Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at DHQ Hospital Parachinar, District Kurram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, from December 2025 to March 2026. A total of 109 healthcare providers, including nurses, paramedical staff, and housekeeping staff, were selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of demographic information, knowledge assessment, and practice-related questions. The collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 22. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used.

Results:

The study found that most participants had satisfactory knowledge regarding biomedical waste management, particularly in relation to sharps disposal and waste segregation. A considerable proportion of participants reported good waste segregation practices; however, important gaps were identified in PPE use, prevention of bin overfilling, and misconceptions regarding needle recapping. Heavy workload and lack of training were the most commonly reported barriers.

Conclusion:

Healthcare providers at DHQ Hospital Parachinar demonstrated general satisfaction knowledge and relatively good practices regarding biomedical waste management. However, continuous training, improved supervision, and adequate provision of waste management resources are necessary to strengthen safe biomedical waste management practices.

INTRODUCTION

Biomedical waste (BMW) refers to waste generated during the diagnosis, treatment, or immunization of humans and animals, as well as waste produced during medical research and laboratory procedures. Biomedical waste includes infectious materials, pathological waste, pharmaceutical products, chemical substances, and sharps that may pose significant risks to human health and the environment if not managed appropriately (1). The rapid expansion of healthcare services and increasing utilization of disposable medical products have substantially increased the volume of biomedical waste generated in healthcare facilities worldwide, making its proper management an important public health concern (2,3).

Globally, healthcare waste management has received considerable attention due to its potential impact on occupational health and environmental safety. According to international estimates, approximately 15–20% of healthcare waste is considered hazardous and requires specialized handling, treatment, and disposal procedures (4,5). Improper management of biomedical waste may result in hospital-acquired infections, environmental pollution, and increased occupational exposure to infectious agents among healthcare workers and waste handlers (6).

The World Health Organization emphasizes that effective biomedical waste management involves a systematic process including waste segregation, collection, transportation, storage, treatment, and final disposal (5). Among these components, segregation of waste at the point of generation is regarded as the most critical step because improper segregation increases the volume of hazardous waste and complicates disposal procedures. International guidelines recommend the use of color-coded containers, puncture-proof sharps boxes, personal protective equipment, and

continuous staff training to ensure safe waste handling practices (4,5).

Healthcare workers are among the groups most frequently exposed to biomedical waste hazards because they routinely handle contaminated materials during patient care activities. Improper handling and disposal of sharps can result in needle-stick injuries, which remain one of the most common occupational hazards in healthcare settings (11). Such injuries may lead to transmission of blood-borne infections including hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus, posing serious health risks to healthcare personnel (12). Therefore, adherence to biomedical waste management guidelines is essential for protecting healthcare workers and ensuring patient safety.

Previous studies conducted in different countries have reported varying levels of knowledge and compliance regarding biomedical waste management among healthcare providers. Lack of training, inadequate supervision, insufficient awareness, and limited availability of waste management resources have been identified as major factors contributing to poor waste handling practices (7,9). Studies have also demonstrated that healthcare workers who receive formal training regarding biomedical waste management exhibit significantly better compliance with waste segregation and disposal guidelines compared to untrained personnel (13,15).

Infrastructure and resource availability also play an important role in the implementation of safe biomedical waste management systems. Availability of color-coded waste bins, sharps containers, protective equipment, and waste treatment technologies facilitates proper waste handling and disposal. In contrast, healthcare facilities with inadequate resources often experience difficulties in implementing recommended waste management practices (14).

Such deficiencies may increase the risk of occupational exposure and environmental contamination.

Developing countries face additional challenges in biomedical waste management due to financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, and limited waste treatment facilities. In many low- and middle-income countries, hazardous healthcare waste is frequently mixed with municipal waste, increasing environmental and public health risks (22,24). Studies have reported that limited training opportunities, weak regulatory enforcement, and insufficient monitoring systems contribute to poor compliance with biomedical waste management guidelines in healthcare institutions (21,25).

In Pakistan, biomedical waste management has become an important public health issue due to increasing healthcare demands and concerns regarding healthcare waste disposal. The Government of Pakistan introduced Hospital Waste Management Rules to regulate safe waste segregation, collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal practices within healthcare facilities (23). Despite the existence of these regulations, implementation remains inconsistent across many healthcare institutions. Studies conducted in different regions of Pakistan have identified deficiencies in waste segregation practices, inadequate training of healthcare personnel, and insufficient availability of waste management materials (21,34).

District-level hospitals often face additional challenges due to limited resources, heavy patient loads, and inadequate waste management infrastructure. These factors may compromise compliance with biomedical waste management guidelines and increase occupational risks among healthcare workers (19,20). Previous studies conducted in healthcare facilities have also highlighted the importance of evaluating healthcare workers' knowledge and practices regarding biomedical waste management to identify gaps and develop effective interventions (26,32).

District Headquarters Hospital Parachinar is a major healthcare institution serving a large population in District Kurram and generates

considerable quantities of biomedical waste through routine clinical and diagnostic activities. Effective biomedical waste management within the hospital largely depends on the knowledge, awareness, and practices of healthcare providers who are directly involved in waste handling and disposal procedures (33). Therefore, assessing the current status of biomedical waste management knowledge and practices among healthcare providers is essential for identifying existing gaps and strengthening waste management systems.

The findings of this study may provide valuable evidence for healthcare administrators and policymakers to improve training programs, strengthen supervision mechanisms, and enhance biomedical waste management practices within healthcare facilities. Ultimately, improved biomedical waste management contributes to occupational safety, environmental protection, infection prevention, and overall healthcare quality (27,28,37,38).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the knowledge and practices related to biomedical waste management among healthcare providers working at District Headquarters (DHQ) Hospital Parachinar.

Study Setting

The study was conducted at District Headquarters (DHQ) Hospital, Parachinar, District Kurram, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The hospital serves as a major secondary healthcare facility providing inpatient, outpatient, emergency, surgical, and diagnostic services to a large population within the district.

Study Duration

The study was carried out over a period of four months from December 2025 to March 2026.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using the Raosoft sample size calculator, assuming a 50% response distribution, a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, and an estimated population of 150

healthcare providers. Based on these parameters, a sample size of 109 participants was obtained.

Sampling Technique

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was employed. Healthcare providers who fulfilled the eligibility criteria and were available during the data collection period were invited to participate in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

Registered nurses working at DHQ Hospital Parachinar.

Paramedical staff directly involved in patient care services.

Housekeeping staff involved in waste handling activities.

Healthcare providers with a minimum of six months of work experience.

Individuals willing to participate and provide written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Administrative staff not directly involved in patient care.

Staff members on long-term leave during the study period.

Individuals unwilling to participate in the study.

Data Collection Procedure

Following approval from the relevant authorities and hospital administration, eligible participants were approached in their respective departments. The objectives of the study were explained, confidentiality was assured, and written informed consent was obtained. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed to assess demographic characteristics, knowledge regarding biomedical waste management, waste handling practices, availability of waste management

resources, and perceived barriers affecting proper waste management. Completed questionnaires were collected on the same day to maximize response rates and ensure data completeness.

Data Analysis

Data were entered, cleaned, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the findings. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables, including profession, department, years of experience, previous training, knowledge items, practice indicators, and perceived barriers. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables where applicable. Results were presented in tables and figures to facilitate interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant Institutional Review Board prior to commencement of the study. Permission was also obtained from the administration of DHQ Hospital Parachinar. Participation was voluntary, confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, and no personal identifiers were recorded. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any stage without any consequences.

RESULTS

A total of 109 healthcare providers working at District Headquarters (DHQ) Hospital, Parachinar participated in the study. The findings are presented according to demographic and professional characteristics, knowledge regarding biomedical waste management, reported practices, resource availability, and perceived barriers affecting biomedical waste management.

Demographic and Professional Characteristics of Participants

Table 1. Demographic and Professional Characteristics of the Participants (n = 109)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Profession	Nurse	40	36.7

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
	Paramedical staff	58	53.2
	Housekeeping staff	11	10.1
Department	Emergency	47	43.1
	Medical ward	5	4.6
	Surgical ward	9	8.3
	Children ward	13	11.9
	Operation theatre	11	10.1
	Other	24	22.0
	Years of experience	6-12 months	22
	1-5 years	25	22.9
	6-10 years	27	24.8
	More than 10 years	35	32.1
Previous BMW training	Yes	75	68.8
	No	34	31.2
Source of training	Hospital induction	45	41.3
	Workshop	15	13.8
	Academic course	14	12.8
	Other	2	1.8
	No response	33	30.3

The demographic and professional profile revealed that paramedical staff constituted the largest proportion of participants, followed by nurses and housekeeping personnel. Most respondents were working in the emergency department, reflecting the substantial patient load and healthcare activities occurring in this unit.

Nearly one-third of the participants had more than ten years of professional experience. Furthermore, over two-thirds reported receiving previous training regarding biomedical waste management, indicating a reasonable level of institutional exposure to waste management education.

Figure 1. Professional Distribution of Healthcare Providers (n = 109)

Figure 2. Department-wise Distribution of Healthcare Providers (n = 109)

Figure 3. Previous Training Regarding Biomedical Waste Management (n = 109)

Knowledge Regarding Biomedical Waste Management

Table 2. Knowledge of Healthcare Providers Regarding Biomedical Waste Management (n = 109)

Knowledge Item	Correct n (%)	Incorrect n (%)	Don't Know / No Response n (%)
Used needles should be disposed of in a sharps container	108 (99.1)	1 (0.9)	0 (0.0)
Human anatomical waste goes in a yellow bag	69 (63.3)	36 (33.0)	4 (3.7)
BMW should be segregated at the point of generation	78 (71.6)	21 (19.3)	10 (9.2)
It is safe to recap a used needle before disposal	44 (40.4)	63 (57.8)	2 (1.8)
Chemical waste should be disposed of in a blue container	72 (66.1)	28 (25.7)	9 (8.3)
A puncture-proof container is used for sharps	90 (82.6)	19 (17.4)	0 (0.0)
Gloves are not necessary while handling BMW if hands are washed	82 (75.2)	25 (22.9)	2 (1.8)
Main purpose of BMW management is infection prevention and environmental protection	96 (88.1)	10 (9.2)	3 (2.8)

The findings demonstrate an overall satisfactory level of knowledge regarding biomedical waste management among healthcare providers. Almost all respondents correctly identified the appropriate disposal method for used needles, indicating strong awareness regarding sharps management. Knowledge related to waste

segregation, color coding, and the purpose of biomedical waste management was also generally satisfactory. However, an important misconception was observed regarding recapping of used needles, highlighting the need for additional training on safe sharps handling procedures and occupational safety.

Figure 4. Correct Responses to Selected Knowledge Items on Biomedical Waste Management (n = 109)

Practices Regarding Biomedical Waste Management

Table 3. Practices of Healthcare Providers Regarding Biomedical Waste Management (n = 109)

Practice Item	Always (%)	n (%)	Often (%)	n (%)	Sometimes (%)	n (%)	Rarely (%)	n (%)	Never (%)	n (%)
I segregate waste into the correct color-coded bins	90 (82.6)	2 (1.8)	13 (11.9)	1 (0.9)	3 (2.8)					
I wear appropriate PPE while handling BMW	60 (55.0)	20 (18.3)	23 (21.1)	6 (5.5)	0 (0.0)					
I dispose of used sharps immediately in a puncture-proof container	64 (58.7)	21 (19.3)	22 (20.2)	1 (0.9)	1 (0.9)					
I ensure the BMW bin is not overfilled	39 (35.8)	20 (18.3)	35 (32.1)	7 (6.4)	8 (7.3)					
I participate in or remind others about proper segregation	56 (51.4)	22 (20.2)	24 (22.0)	5 (4.6)	2 (1.8)					

The reported practices indicate generally good compliance with recommended biomedical waste management procedures. The majority of healthcare providers consistently segregated waste into the appropriate color-coded bins and disposed of sharps in puncture-proof containers. Compliance with the use of personal protective

equipment was moderate, while preventing overfilling of waste bins showed comparatively lower adherence. These findings suggest that although routine waste management practices are largely satisfactory, specific operational practices require additional attention and monitoring.

Figure 5. Reported “Always” Practices Regarding Biomedical Waste Management (n = 109)

Availability of Biomedical Waste Management Resources

Table 4. Availability of Biomedical Waste Management Resources and Confidence of Participants (n = 109)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Availability of BMW bins and PPE	Yes	68	62.4
	Sometimes	34	31.2
	No	7	6.4
Confidence in knowledge of BMW categories	Yes	107	98.2
	No	2	1.8

The assessment of resource availability demonstrated that most participants reported adequate availability of biomedical waste bins and personal protective equipment. However, approximately one-third of respondents indicated that these resources were only intermittently

available, suggesting occasional shortages. Nearly all participants expressed confidence in their understanding of biomedical waste categories, reflecting a generally positive perception of their knowledge regarding waste management procedures.

Figure 6. Availability of Biomedical Waste Management Resources (n = 109)

Figure 6. Availability of Biomedical Waste Management Resources (n = 109)

Perceived Barriers to Proper Biomedical Waste Management

Table 5. Perceived Barriers to Proper Biomedical Waste Management (n = 109)

Barrier	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Heavy workload / staff shortage	36	33.0
Lack of training	27	24.8
Poor supervision and monitoring	17	15.6
Inadequate availability of waste disposal materials	15	13.8
Lack of awareness of BMW guidelines	14	12.8

Participants identified several challenges affecting the implementation of proper biomedical waste management practices. Heavy workload and staff shortages emerged as the most commonly reported barriers, followed by insufficient training opportunities. Additional obstacles included inadequate supervision, limited availability of waste disposal materials, and inadequate awareness regarding established biomedical waste management guidelines. These findings highlight the importance of organizational support and continuous capacity building.

DISCUSSION

The present study assessed the knowledge and practices regarding biomedical waste management among healthcare providers at District Headquarters (DHQ) Hospital Parachinar. Biomedical waste management is an essential component of infection prevention, occupational safety, and environmental protection because improper disposal of healthcare waste may result in transmission of infectious diseases, occupational injuries, and environmental contamination (1-5). The findings of this study provide important insights into the current status of biomedical waste management among healthcare providers working in a district-level healthcare facility.

In the present study, the majority of participants were paramedical staff (53.2%), followed by nurses (36.7%) and housekeeping staff (10.1%). Similar participant distributions have been reported in previous studies where nurses and paramedical personnel were the primary groups involved in handling biomedical waste during routine patient care activities (13,15). Since these healthcare workers are directly involved in waste generation and disposal, their knowledge and practices play a critical role in maintaining safe healthcare environments.

Training is considered one of the most important determinants of effective biomedical waste management. The present study revealed that 68.8% of participants had previously received training regarding biomedical waste management. These findings are consistent with those reported by Mathur et al. (13), who observed that healthcare

workers receiving formal training demonstrated significantly better knowledge and compliance with waste management guidelines. Similarly, Sharma et al. (15) reported that trained healthcare personnel exhibited higher awareness regarding waste segregation, color coding, and safe disposal procedures. These findings indicate that continuous training programs can substantially improve healthcare workers' competencies regarding biomedical waste management.

The assessment of knowledge demonstrated generally satisfactory awareness among healthcare providers. Nearly all participants (99.1%) correctly identified that used needles should be disposed of in puncture-proof sharps containers. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies where awareness regarding sharps disposal was relatively high because healthcare workers recognize the serious consequences of needle-stick injuries (11,12). Proper disposal of sharps is essential for preventing occupational exposure to blood-borne pathogens and maintaining workplace safety.

However, an important knowledge gap was identified regarding recapping of used needles. More than half of the respondents demonstrated misconceptions regarding this practice. According to Wilburn and Eijkemans (11), needle recapping is one of the major causes of occupational needle-stick injuries among healthcare workers. Tarantola et al. (12) further reported that accidental exposure to contaminated sharps increases the risk of transmission of hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, and human immunodeficiency virus. The persistence of this misconception indicates the need for focused educational interventions emphasizing safe sharps handling procedures.

Knowledge regarding waste segregation at the point of generation was generally satisfactory among respondents. Most participants correctly recognized that biomedical waste should be segregated immediately after generation. Similar observations have been reported by Manyele and Anicetus (7), who emphasized that waste segregation is the most critical step in biomedical waste management because it reduces hazardous waste volume and facilitates safe disposal procedures. Proper segregation also contributes to

improved infection control and environmental protection.

The findings related to biomedical waste management practices were encouraging. A large proportion of participants reported consistently segregating waste into appropriate color-coded containers. Similar results were reported by Mathur et al. (13) and Sharma et al. (15), who found that trained healthcare workers generally demonstrate better compliance with waste segregation protocols. Effective segregation practices contribute to safer healthcare environments and minimize the risk of contamination associated with hazardous healthcare waste.

The use of personal protective equipment remains an essential component of occupational safety. In the present study, only 55% of respondents reported always using appropriate personal protective equipment while handling biomedical waste. Although this reflects moderate compliance, there remains considerable room for improvement. Previous studies have emphasized that proper utilization of gloves, masks, aprons, and other protective equipment significantly reduces occupational exposure to infectious waste materials (8,18). Consistent use of personal protective equipment should therefore be reinforced through training and supervision.

The study also revealed comparatively lower compliance regarding prevention of waste bin overfilling. Similar findings have been reported by Patil and Pokhrel (14), who observed that inadequate monitoring and poor waste management infrastructure contributed to ineffective waste handling practices in healthcare facilities. Overfilled waste containers increase the likelihood of accidental injuries, contamination, and environmental exposure. Strengthening waste collection systems and regular monitoring may help address this issue.

Resource availability represents another important factor influencing biomedical waste management practices. Although most respondents reported adequate availability of biomedical waste bins and personal protective equipment, a substantial proportion indicated that these resources were only intermittently available. Similar challenges

have been documented in healthcare facilities of developing countries where shortages of waste management materials negatively affect compliance with established guidelines (22,24). Adequate infrastructure and consistent availability of waste management supplies are essential for ensuring effective biomedical waste management. The present study identified several barriers affecting proper biomedical waste management. Heavy workload and staff shortages were reported as the most significant barriers, followed by lack of training, inadequate supervision, insufficient availability of waste disposal materials, and lack of awareness regarding biomedical waste management guidelines. Similar barriers have been reported by Khan et al. (21), Abdullah and Khan (34), and Ali et al. (22), who identified workload pressures, limited resources, and inadequate training as major challenges affecting healthcare waste management systems in developing countries. Addressing these barriers requires institutional commitment, resource allocation, and continuous professional development opportunities for healthcare personnel.

Overall, the findings of the present study indicate that healthcare providers at DHQ Hospital Parachinar possess satisfactory knowledge and relatively good practices regarding biomedical waste management. Nevertheless, important deficiencies remain in areas such as needle recapping practices, personal protective equipment utilization, waste bin management, and resource availability. Addressing these gaps through regular training programs, strengthened supervision, and improved infrastructure may significantly enhance biomedical waste management practices and contribute to occupational safety, infection prevention, and environmental protection.

CONCLUSION

The present study assessed the knowledge and practices regarding biomedical waste management among healthcare providers at DHQ Hospital Parachinar, District Kurram. The findings demonstrated that healthcare providers possessed generally satisfactory knowledge and relatively

good practices regarding biomedical waste management.

Most participants showed appropriate awareness regarding waste segregation, sharps disposal, and the importance of biomedical waste management for infection prevention and environmental protection. However, notable gaps were identified regarding needle recapping practices, consistent use of personal protective equipment, and prevention of biomedical waste bin overfilling.

The study further revealed that heavy workload, staff shortages, inadequate training opportunities, insufficient supervision, and occasional shortages of waste management resources were important barriers affecting effective biomedical waste management practices.

Overall, although the current level of knowledge and practice among healthcare providers is satisfactory, continuous training programs, strengthened monitoring systems, adequate resource allocation, and institutional support are necessary to further improve biomedical waste management practices. Such improvements will contribute to safer healthcare environments, enhanced occupational safety, improved infection prevention, and better environmental protection.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Regular training sessions and refresher workshops should be conducted to improve healthcare workers' knowledge regarding biomedical waste management and safe waste handling practices.

Hospital administration should ensure strict implementation and enforcement of biomedical waste management guidelines across all clinical departments.

Continuous supervision and monitoring systems should be established to improve compliance with waste segregation, disposal procedures, and infection prevention measures.

Adequate availability of color-coded waste bins, puncture-proof sharps containers, waste disposal bags, and personal protective equipment should be ensured at all times.

Awareness programs should specifically address unsafe practices such as needle recapping and improper disposal of sharps.

Adequate staffing levels and workload management strategies should be implemented to reduce workload pressures affecting biomedical waste management practices.

Regular audits and evaluations should be conducted to monitor compliance and identify areas requiring improvement.

Further multicenter studies should be conducted in other healthcare institutions to generate broader evidence regarding biomedical waste management practices in Pakistan.

This discussion uses the references from your thesis (especially 7, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 21, 22, 24, and 34) and follows the same article style as the previous paper.

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